

Efficacy of temephos and permethrin in black fly (*Simulium spp*) control and their effect on non-target entomofauna in a portion of Sanaga Valley in Cameroon

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Abstract

The biodiversity in the Congo Basin can be at once a blessing and a curse. A good example of a curse is the abundance of insects that cause nuisance and morbidity in this area especially onchocerciasis transmitted by black fly (*Simulium spp*) which is a major problem in disturbed environments (climate change). Black fly bites reduce the duration a man can work and increase the likelihood of the transmission of onchocerciasis (river blindness) in the tropical rainforest area of Cameroon. In order to decrease nuisance and morbidity caused by black fly and improve farmers' productivity, a study was conducted between 2007 and 2009 in a portion of Sanaga Valley in Cameroon (Monatele (04° 09 N, 11° 01 E), Ossebe (04° 03 N, 10° 36 E), Songndong (03° 51 N, 10° 15 E), Batombe (03° 51 N, 10° 10 E) and Ka'a (04° 43 N, 12° 24 E)), one of

the most infected zones of the country. Black fly and non-target insects captured were identified using identification keys. Data recorded on sticky traps and artificial breeding sites were used to evaluate the efficacy of temephos and permethrin, and their impact on non-target associated entomofauna in the reproduction sites of *Simulium damnosum*. Both larvicides, temephos and permethrin, are effective in the control of black fly though permethrin caused limited undesirable effects on non-target species. Insects of the Order Odonata were more affected by permethrin than insects of the Orders Ephemeroptera, Plecoptera and Tricoptera (EPT), which are the most vulnerable orders. This means that it has limited environmental effects when sprayed as specified in this trial and can be used in the integrated vector management of black fly.

Keywords: spraying, non-target organisms, resistance, black fly, Cameroon

Résumé

La biodiversité dans le Bassin du Congo peut être à la fois une bénédiction et une malédiction. Un bel exemple de la malédiction est l'abondance des insectes qui causent la nuisance et la morbidité dans cette zone et spécialement l'onchocercose transmise par la mouche noire (*Simulium spp*), ce qui représente un problème majeur dans un environnement aujourd'hui perturbé par les changements climatiques. Les piqûres de la mouche noire (*Simulium spp*) ont des conséquences néfastes sur le temps de travail des agriculteurs vivant dans les zones situées le long de la vallée du fleuve Sanaga. En plus, elles transmettent le parasite *Onchocerca volvulus* responsable de l'onchocercose ou cécité des rivières. Afin de diminuer ces nuisances et réduire la morbidité causée par l'onchocercose et améliorer la productivité, une étude a été menée entre 2007 et 2009 dans une portion de la Vallée de la Sanaga au Cameroun (Monatele (04° 09 N, 11° 01 E), Ossebe (04° 03 N, 10° 36 E), Songndong (03° 51 N, 10° 15 E), Batombe (03° 51 N,

10° 10 E) et Ka'a (04° 43 N, 12° 24 E)), l'une des zones les plus infestées du pays. Des simulies collectées à l'aide des pièges d'interception à glue et des gîtes larvaires artificiels puis des insectes non-cibles collectés par la méthode du kick sampling, ont été identifiés en se servant des clés d'identification. Les comptages ont servi à l'évaluation de l'efficacité du temephos et de la perméthrine, ainsi que leur impact sur la faune entomologique associée, là où *Simulium damnosum* est trouvée. Les deux larvicides ont montré leur efficacité pour le contrôle de la mouche noire, toutefois avec des effets indésirables limités de la perméthrine sur les espèces non-cibles. Les Odonates ont montré une sensibilité relativement élevée à la perméthrine par rapport aux Ephemeroptères, Plécoptères et Tricoptères (EPT) qui sont généralement les ordres les plus vulnérables. Ceci signifie que l'utilisation de la perméthrine dans les conditions de cette étude a un effet minimal sur l'environnement et peut être utilisé dans la lutte intégrée contre la mouche noire.

mots clés : Pulvérisation, organismes non-cibles, résistance, mouche noire, Cameroun

1. Introduction

The forests of the Congo Basin constitute the second largest continuous tropical forest mass in the world after the Amazon and represent approximately 20% of the world's remaining closed tropical canopy. These forests do not only play a significant role for global biodiversity conservation but also essential global ecological services as carbon sink and as a fresh water catchment basin. Seventy-five million people depend on these natural resources for their survival in a unique ecosystem that is endangered by deforestation, poaching, over-fishing, mining and construction especially dams for hydroelectricity generation.

Approximately 80% of all animal species on earth are insects. They are pollinators, undertakers, leaf litter sweepers, garbage collectors, soil conditioners and natural fertilizer producers by nature but also disease agents (Leslie Saul, 1999). Some of these insects include mosquitoes (*Anopheles spp*, *Culex spp*, *Aedes spp*), black flies (*Simulium spp*) and tsetse flies (*Glossina spp*). In many countries, there is a major problem of implementation of vector control, which cannot enable poor people living in rural areas to benefit from expensive technology (Matthews et al., 2009). Vector control using aerial application of larvicides was the initial strategy of the Onchocerciasis Control Programme (OCP), with the aim of interrupting onchocerciasis transmission. It was hypothesised that maintaining this control strategy for 14 years would result in adult onchocercal parasites dying out naturally in human hosts. This strategy was successful in the central OCP areas (about 1 million km²) in nine countries where onchocerciasis infection and transmission were eliminated and where active control could cease and be replaced by surveillance (Boatin et Richard, 2006).

Ground larviciding was another option used successfully in Sanaga River near Mbandjock area in Cameroon (Baldet et al., 1997) and in Bioko an Island of Equatorial Guinea (Cheke et al., 2009). Studies reported by Traore et al. (2009) and Cheke et al. (2009) in Bioko showed that the distribution of ivermectin (an active ingredient of mectizan used for the treatment of onchocerciasis) had not decreased the prevalence of the disease, but when vector control was applied for four months by treating the rivers with larvicides, the vector *Simulium yahense*, a member of the *S. damnosum Edwardsi* complex, the only species present in this area disappeared and not only was the disease incidence eliminated but the nuisance became non-existent. Therefore, vector control is a

more efficient way of controlling many insect borne diseases. Adequate strategies should thus be developed to improve vector control at affordable costs.

One particularity of onchocerciasis, a disease transmitted by the black fly is that it is a major health problem in the Congo basin, although it is classified as a neglected tropical disease due to its geographical restriction. Another particularity is the fact that it becomes a serious health concern only in modified environments. In Cameroon, it is a public health problem mostly along the points where dams have been constructed for electricity generation. The southern forest residents depend on farming (cocoa, coffee, maize, cassava, oil palm) and fishing unfortunately the high biting rate of black fly (nuisance) and disease transmission (morbidity) reduce the time of work.

Vector control is an important component in the prevention and control of vector-borne disease, especially for transmission control. Vector management as a cross-cutting activity develops and promotes strategies, guidelines and standards for vector control, including sound management of pesticides. It promotes integrated vector management to improve efficacy, cost-effectiveness, ecological soundness and suitability of vector control interventions for vector-borne disease control. However, the vector control activities should not only be effective but also should not reduce the population of non-target invertebrates. This study was therefore aimed at comparing the efficacy of two commercial larvicides based on permethrin and temephos, used in Simuliidae control and their effect on non-target entomofauna in *S. damnosum* breeding sites.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Study area: Trials were conducted in five locations; Monatele (04°09N, 11°01E), Ossebe (04°03N, 10°36E), Songndong (03°51N, 10°15E), Batombe (03°51N, 10°10E) and Ka'a (04°43N, 12°24E) with altitudes ranging from 69 to 293m above sea level.

2.2. Identification of black fly species: Larvae and pupae were collected from substrates in water in a wide range of biotopes within fast flowing sections of the river including stones and trailing vegetation. Collections were conducted either by removing the larvae and the pupae directly by hand from the substrate or using a net of 250µm mesh size held downstream of the collection point prior to the removal of stones from the water. The plant substrate was then carried to the river bank where attached

larvae and pupae were removed with fine pair of tweezers. Larvae and pupae were transported to the laboratory in containers of natural water maintained on ice in a cool box. This system provided enough oxygenation for the survival of the species so that identification could be done the following day. Adults were caught on sticky traps.

2.3. Identification of non-target organisms: Hand collection and netting were used for the collection of non-target invertebrates. Collection of many aquatic insects was done with hands or forceps. Insects were picked up from the substrates such as rocks, logs, sticks, leaves or even human trash and transferred into a vial of alcohol. Kick samples of macro invertebrates were collected with a net (800µm mesh) in wadeable portion of the river. Four 3-minute samples were taken on the sampling visit to include all different substrates and flow regime zones. Samples collected from the net were preserved in 70% ethanol. Insects were observed on a dissecting microscope followed by compound microscopes (40x) after immersion in 10% potassium hydrochloride and keys were used to identify the insects based on certain features including cervical sclerites (Crosskey, 1969). For non-target organisms, the field Guides to the freshwater invertebrates of southern Africa was used for identification (Day et al., 2002; de Moor et al., 2002).

2.4. Larviciding: For the application of the larvicide, a system of spraying was developed consisting of a local wooden boat (pirogue) of two tanks equipped with an outboard two stroke engine (YAMAHA) of 8 horse power, together with a motorised spray pump and two lances each equipped with two outlets (4 nozzles). After initial tests, nozzles were fitted at the maximum output of the pump were used to provide a flow rate of 2.5l/minute from each of the four outlets. Three persons were responsible for the spray operation; engine operator, pump operator and an assistant filling the containers. Appropriate safety measures were put in place for spraying in the fast flowing river. The lances used were of plastic material to resist corrosivity. Wooden boats were easy to fabricate in the forest areas and measured 5m long by 1.5 m large and 0.8m deep. Spraying operations were performed across River Sanaga at each point. The number of spraying points depended on the carry of the larvicide.

2.5. Efficacy of treatments: This was performed using larval and adult mortality counting. Larval mortality was done according to the method described by Dejoux (1975). Artificial breeding sites consisting of yellow cotton tissues of 50x5cm were fixed in the natural

breeding sites (rapids) to substitute natural substrates. They were removed and placed again after the larvae were counted. Larval stages of *Simulium* species attached to them were removed and preserved in 70% ethanol, labelled with dates and sites of collection, and taken to the laboratory for identification and counting. Counting the number of larvae on the substrates before and after spraying by checking the mortality of larvae was done at two breeding sites which consisted of artificial breeding sites placed in the points in order to evaluate the larval mortality. For temephos, the three checking points were situated respectively at 20, 30 and 50 km downstream from the spraying point. For permethrin the checking points were placed 6, 10 and 12 km downstream from the spraying point. Larvae and pupae were counted 4h before each treatment and 4 and 24h after each treatment.

Adult counting done by estimation of daily adult black flies trapped on 1m² transparent screen (sticky trap) was conducted before, during and after application.

They were held vertically at 0.5m above the ground generally on the trees or shrubs hanging on two pieces of wire at 100 m from the river and in places with high population densities. The flying insects stuck onto the glue and black flies were removed and counted. The traps were placed 24h before spraying and trapped insects were counted daily.

2.6. Assessment of the effect of larvicides on non-target species: Assessment of the effect on non-target species was conducted by comparing the presence of orders of insects before and after the treatment. The presence of the sensitive orders like Ephemeroptera, Plecoptera and Tricoptera (EPT) indicates that the larvicide is not harmful. In contrast any increase in density of Chiridomidae (Diptera) is an indicator of the high level of pollution having provoked the elimination of natural enemies (Arimoro et al., 2007).

2.7. Data analysis: Analyses were performed using SPSS version 17.0. The difference between the quantity of pesticide used and cost were obtained by comparing the means using the Student t-test.

3. Results

3.1. Identification of black fly species: One hundred and twenty species of adult black fly were captured at different points situated 800m along the river and 350m from the river edge and where the traps were placed at a height between 0 to 12m (maximum height sampled). All the samples observed under the microscope at the 40x magnification had the first five abdominal segments with paired dorsolateral

subconical tubercles ; cuticle of the entire body, including anterior proleg, covered with elongated scale-like setae. After this series of laboratory and eye identification of sampled black fly species, it was concluded that they all belong to the *S. damnosum* Edwards complex.

3.2. Identification of non-target insects: Tables 1 and 2 show the different orders, families and taxons identified after collection of insects as well as the quantities by orders. 9,468 insects were collected from 2007 to 2009 with 18 species, 10 families and 7 orders. Non-target insects were classified into seven orders.

Coleoptera was the highest number followed by the Diptera while Oligochaeta was the least collected order (table 2). Eighteen non-target insect species were identified belonging to ten families. The most represented family was Chironomidae with five species followed by Baetidae with three species. The other families were represented by one or two species each (table 1).

3.3. Larviciding: The monthly mean discharges of the river varied from 847m³/s in February during the dry season, to 5,188m³/s in October during the rainy season. The quantity of Abate 500E subsequently varied from

Table 1: Orders, families and species of non-target insects identified during the study

Order	Family	Species
Oligochaeta	Naididae	<i>Derodigitata</i>
Ephemeroptera	Baetidae	<i>Baetis sp.</i>
		<i>Pseudocloeoncyindrical</i>
		<i>Pseudocloeonrpisces</i>
Plecoptera	Perlidae	<i>Neoperla sp.</i>
Trichoptera	Leptoceridae	<i>Leptocerina sp.</i>
		<i>Athripsodes sp</i>
Coleoptera	Dystiscidae	<i>Philodytes sp.</i>
		<i>Philaccolus sp.</i>
	Notonectidae	<i>Hydrocanthus sp.</i>
Odonata	Libellulidae	<i>Brachythemis lacustris</i>
Diptera	Chironomidae	<i>Chironomus</i>
		<i>Cryptochironomus sp.</i>
		<i>Pentaneura sp.</i>
		<i>Tanypus sp.</i>
		<i>Tanytarsus sp.</i>
	Culicidae	<i>Culex pipiens</i>
	Ceratopogonidae	<i>Forcipomyia sp.</i>

Table 2: Number of non-target insects and their relative percentages collected during the 3-year period of study

Order	Number collected in 2007		Number collected in 2008		Number collected in 2009	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Ephemeroptera	405	13.19	459	16.12	602	16.96
Plecoptera	501	16.32	399	14.091	459	12.93
Trichoptera	428	13.94	400	14.04	512	14.42
Odonata	389	12.67	401	14.08	432	12.17
Coleoptera	506	16.48	500	17.56	603	16.99
Diptera	542	17.65	412	14.47	543	15.30
Oligochaeta	299	9.74	277	9.73	399	11.24
Total	3070	100	2848	100	3550	100

406.56 litres to 2490.24 litres during the same period, and for Permetalm 200EC, the variation was 152.44 litres to 933.84 litres for one operational spraying.

Figure 1: Larvae variation counted in 12 sprayings at Batombe 4 hours before, 4 and 24 hours after spraying with Permethrin 200EC in 2008

Figure 2 : Larvae variation counted in 12 sprayings at Songdong 4 hours before, 4 and 24 hours after spraying with Permethrin 200EC in 2008

Figure 3: Variation of the densities of adult black fly caught in the sticky traps before, during and after the treatment with permethrin 200EC in 2008

3.4. Efficacy of treatments: Larval and adult counting from artificial breeding sites and sticky traps done respectively, before and after treatments in 2008 at Batombe and Songdong sites gave the following results in figures 1, 2 and 3.

3.5. Assessment of the effect of the two larvicides on non-target insects: In order to establish the possible effects of the larvicides on the non-target insects used in the study, in situ or semi-field evaluations conducted using the multiple gutters system gave the following results. For temephos, two operational concentrations (0.1mg/l and the half 0.05mg/l) and the control with no chemical were tested for 24 hours. 788 individuals were tested with a concentration of 0.1mg/l and the percentage of drifted fauna was 12.5%. Using a concentration of 0.05mg/l in 784 individuals, the drift due to the insecticide was 8.4%. In the control gutter out of 803 individuals tested 69 drifted in 24 hours giving a percentage of 6.4%.

Equally, in situ tests were conducted to assess the effects of permethrin on non-target organisms. After 24 hours of exposure with a concentration of 0.015mg/l, the percentage of drifted fauna was 18.85%. Using a concentration of 0.008mg/l, the drift due to the insecticide was 10.93%. The overall results (table 4) showed a variation on the species drift. Diptera, Odonata and Ephemeroptera were more susceptible while Coleoptera and Oligochaeta were less affected. In the three control gutters, only 9.58, 9.55, and 9.22 % of the insects were drifted in 2007, 2008 and 2009, respectively.

4. Discussion

4.1. Identification of black fly species: Previous studies conducted in the Sanaga River have shown that the species found in this river is *S. squamosum* B, a member of the *S. damnosum* complex. This study has confirmed the status of the species found in the study area as belonging to *S. damnosum* complex.

4.2. Identification of non-target insects: Identification of the non-target insects collected showed the presence of different orders, families and species. The study of Arimoro and Ikomi (2009) on aquatic fauna in tropical areas in the Niger Delta, Nigeria identified the same orders and families obtained in this study. Comparison of the total number of insects collected in the same sample sites during three successive years did not show (p=0.38) any decline in the populations of non-target insects. However, statistical comparison of the number of insects sampled by means of Fisher (p=0.0000) showed some differences among the sampled orders with significantly high numbers in four orders:

Odonota, Ephemeroptera, Plecoptera and Tricoptera. This difference between the orders of insects was observed before and after spraying. This clearly demonstrates that changes in the population are not related to the use of larvicides. Previous studies by Arimoro et al. (2007) have shown that the three orders Ephemeroptera, Plecoptera and Tricoptera (EPT) are very vulnerable to high pollution. However, during this study there was no clear sign of decline of the EPT population. This could mean that the treatments of this portion of the river with the two larvicides; permethrin and temephos from 2007 to 2009 did not pollute the river to a level that could affect the non-target insect populations.

4.3. Larviciding: In 2009, about 2982.12 litres of temephos and 1118.29 litres of permethrin were used during 21 weekly treatments. In terms of cost, permethrin is cheaper compared to temephos. However, temephos is good because it disintegrates faster in the environment.

4.4. Efficacy of treatments: The main aim of the ground larviciding activities carried out in this study

was achieved with little satisfaction because parts of River Sanaga were inaccessible for treatments particularly when using Permetalm 200EC, which has shorter carry than Abate 500E. The low levels of recovery to pre-control levels of fly populations in the areas treated revealed that the reduction of the population of Simulium species below the nuisance level can be achieved. The two larvicides used have proved to be efficacious after entomological evaluation and human perception.

Other studies with permethrin based larvicides have given good results with a decrease in the population of black fly (Hougard et al., 1992; Baldet et al., 1997) but due to the suspicion of harmful effect of permethrin on non-target aquatic fauna, particularly vertebrates, it was advised that this chemical should not be used more than eighth times in a year (Cheke et al., 1997).

Cheke et al. (2009) used temephosto eliminate Simulium yahense from Bioko in Equatorial Guinea. This compound was also used in the OCP program with success but after four successive years, resistance was developed. After years of withdrawal due to

Table 3: Percentage of insects detached after 24 hours in the gutter at 0.05 mg/l and 0.1mg/l of temephos (Four replicates each year)

Order	2007			2008			2009		
	0.1mg/l	0.05mg/l	Control	0.1mg/l	0.05mg/l	Control	0.1mg/l	0.05mg/l	Control
Diptera	19.7	13.3	1,4	18.8	13.6	1.3	19.4	13.2	1,5
Ephemeroptera	17.1	13.7	6.4	17.5	13.5	7.0	17.2	13.7	7,3
Trichoptera	12.7	8.2	7.2	13.1	8.4	6.8	13.5	7.9	6.3
Plecoptera	5.7	4.3	2.7	5.5	4.6	2.4	4.9	13.8	2.6
Coleoptera	7.3	3.9	5.5	7.8	3.8	5.3	7.3	4.3	5.7
Odonata	17.2	10.2	9.3	17.6	17.0	9.7	17.8	17.4	9.5
Oligochaeta	8.1	2.1	5.8	7.9	2.4	5.2	7.5	2.2	5.6
Average	12.54	7.9	7.0	12.60	7.0	5.2	12.5	10.3	5.3

Table 4: Percentage of insects detached after 24 hours in the gutter at 0,015 mg/l and 0.008mg/l of permethrin (Four replicates each year)

Taxa	2007			2008			2009		
	0.015mg/l	0.008mg/l	control	0.015mg/l	0.008mg/l	control	0.015mg/l	0.008mg/l	control
Diptera	30.5	16.1	2.0	29.8	16.3	2.2	31.4	16.3	2.3
Ephemeroptera	23.1	13.4	14.7	23.5	12.9	14.2	22.9	14.1.	13.7
Trichoptera	19.7	9.2	9.2	20.1	9.6	9.8	20.2	9.1	9.7
Plecoptera	12.1	13	14.9	12.3	14.1	14.5	12.3	13.2	13.1
Coleoptera	11.3	5.5	5.9	10.8	5.3	5.6	11.7	5.0	3.9
Odonata	21.2	11.3	18.2	21.6	11.8	18.5	22.0	10.5	18.7
Oligochaeta	13	7.7	2.2	13.2	7.9	2.1	13.1	7.2	3.2
Average	18.7	10.88	9.58	18.75	11.12	9.55	19.08	10.77	9.22

black fly resistance, a considerable improvement in the situation of resistance to it was noted again. However, to avoid development of further resistance, temephos was again applied but in rotation with other operational insecticides (Hougard et al., 1993). It is important to spray a large surface area to avoid early recolonisation of breeding sites (Leveque et al., 2003).

The method of the assessment of the nuisance threshold before spraying used in 2007 in the area of Ossebe and Monatele with Abate 500E showed that the larval population started decreasing only four hours after treatments. Adult black fly number dropped two weeks after the beginning of the treatments. The reduction of the insect population after intervention should have been greater without fly migration from remote untreated areas situated upstream the treated areas and tributaries. The level of nuisance threshold was only reached again three months after the suspension of the treatment. This demonstrated that in this portion only four series of treatments are needed in a year to maintain the nuisance below a threshold. However, if treatments are conducted further upstream, fewer numbers of series of treatments will be required.

4.5. Assessment of effect on non-targets : The overall results showed that Odonata and Ephemeroptera were more susceptible to the larvicides used while Coleoptera and Oligochaeta were less affected. Tests on non-target organisms showed a slight change in behaviour. Higher percentages of detachment were observed at concentrations, 0.1 mg/l of temephos and 0.015 mg/l of permethrin.

Multivariate Analysis of Variance (in General Linear Model) was globally significant ($P < 0.01$) and even for each taxon at 99% confidence level for both temephos and permethrin. However, group comparison test of Newmann and Keuls showed no significant difference ($P > 0.01$) in percentage of insects detached after 24 hours in the gutter at 0.05 mg/l, 0.1 mg/l for temephos for some taxa like Plecoptera and Odonata. There was a significant difference ($P < 0.01$) in percentage of insects detached after 24 hours with the 0.015 mg/l, 0.008 mg/l for permethrin and control for Diptera, Ephemeroptera, Trichoptera, Plecoptera, Coleoptera and Odonata.

Tests in gutters on non-target aquatic insect contribute to evaluate the safety margin between the estimated operational amount and the dose likely to cause an undesirable impact (Yameogo et al., 1991). Doses of 0.1mg/l and 0.015mg/l were acceptable for the two operational larvicides used during the study (results of Homogeneous Newmann and Keuls test). The results

obtained before and after spraying indicated that, the non-target insects were not affected after three years of spraying. This aligns with the results obtained by Leveque et al. (1979) and Kurtak et al. (1987) when in the OCP, an aquatic monitoring program of rivers planned to be regularly treated with insecticides was set up and implemented to satisfy major concerns such as the prevention of the irreversible loss of aquatic biodiversity in West Africa.

5. Conclusion

Temephos and permethrin killed more than 90% of the larvae of black fly after 24 hours at carries of 50 and 10 km, respectively. Whereas only limited undesirable effects are caused by permethrin on non-target species, no effect was noticed with temephos. Insects of the order Odonata were more affected by permethrin than insects of the Ephemeroptera, Plecoptera and Tricoptera which are known to be the most vulnerable orders.

In order to reduce the effects of the black fly for a longer period, it will be important to conduct further entomological evaluation using advanced techniques like cytotaxonomy in order to identify the current profile of Simulium species and sub-species. Screen other larvicides used in Cameroon to assess their efficacy and their effects on non-target organisms.

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